

The potential and pitfalls of artificial intelligence techniques in tumour detection

(invited)

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Cutting-edge AI technologies have the potential to enable new models of care, improve disease prevention and enhance quality of life. These advances can pave the way for increasingly personalised, accessible, efficient and sustainable health and care systems.

The field of radiology holds great promise for the use of artificial intelligence and image processing methods. AI-powered applications can help radiologists optimise their diagnostic workflow, as they have the potential to improve the objectivity and reproducibility of radiological assessments. This is particularly beneficial in high-stress environments where sustained attention over long periods of work is a challenge. By performing tasks tirelessly and consistently, AI-based applications can reduce the burden on clinicians, by helping them prioritizing cases that demand heightened scrutiny, such as in cancer screenings where expeditious assessment of suspicious cases is vital.

Furthermore, the integration of machine learning and data science tools proves fruitful in the identification and consistent measurement of new biomarkers, facilitating, for instance, the prediction of tumour aggressiveness. Ultimately, AI tools can prove indispensable in bolstering resources for less well-equipped facilities, offering techniques to enhance data resolution. These instances represent a mere glimpse into the potential benefits of AI methodologies in the field of radiology.

Nevertheless, the use of AI technologies in clinical practice is still limited. Recent surveys have shown that many clinicians believe that AI solutions could improve their specialty. However, the vast majority of them have never used any AI-powered applications in their daily practice, and only a few consider themselves to have excellent knowledge of the field. Barriers to the adoption of new technologies include challenges to human autonomy, accountability, and liability, as well as potential biases and risks. In addition, users may experience dissatisfaction with user interfaces and find the effort and cognitive load required to use the technology excessive. Overall, there is a reported lack of trust in AI-powered tools, which may be related to a lack of understanding about their assumptions, limitations, and capabilities. High-quality scientific foundations, technical robustness, and responsible development are the only ways to overcome these concerns.

This talk will provide an overview of the most recent advancements in the field, as well as recent international initiatives to ensure AI trustworthiness, such as the FUTURE-AI guidelines.

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